

TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IMPLEMENTATION IN THE DIVISION OF RIZAL: A BASIS FOR PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the total quality management (TQM) of implementation of Inclusive Education (IE) for learners with special educational needs (LSENs) or learners with disabilities (LWDs) among public senior high schools (SHS) in the Division of Rizal. The researcher used the quantitative method, specifically, the descriptive survey design to gather data from the administrators, teachers, and parents of LSENs from eight (8) public SHSs with identified LWDs in the School Year 2023-2024. The study revealed that TQM of IE implementation for LSENs was highly implemented in all the principles of TQM namely: commitment of top management, customer focus, process management, instituting training on the job, instituting leadership, driving out fear, eliminating management by objectives, removing barriers to pride in workmanship, implementing education and self-improvement, and making transformation a job for everyone at work. The responses of administrators, teachers, and parents had a significant difference in terms of removing barriers to pride in workmanship; and Implementing education and self-improvement for everyone. Lastly, the administrators and teachers found the inclusive education implementation for LWDs very challenging because of the lack of training of teachers. On the other hand, the administrators and teachers found it only moderately challenging as regards having lack of support from higher officials and LGUs; lack of awareness, support, and participation from parents; having limited interventions and services at the school level; unclear implementation down to classroom level; having lack of initiatives in enhancing community awareness and relationship; lack of physical facilities and equipment; and there was a poor monitoring and evaluation process.

Keywords: *Total Quality Management, Inclusive Education, Learners with Special Educational Needs, Learners with Disabilities, SNED Program, Senior High School, Polytechnic University of the Philippines, Doctor in Education Management*

INTRODUCTION

According to the data from societies worldwide, around 240 million, or one in every ten children, have a disability of some kind, which raises serious concerns about providing equal access and quality education (UNICEF, 2021). Hence, equity and quality education, which specifically addresses such issues can likely lead to appropriate skill and career development. It is the reason why some global organizations and agencies intensify inclusive education (IE).

The Sub-Education Review Report on IE by UNESCO (2021) pointed out the opportunities for learners with disabilities, whether physical, mental, social, or emotional in Asian Countries, including the Philippines, to receive assistance, access, and equal participation in education. However, there were challenges faced by these countries in inclusion implementation especially that they had to address global concerns. Concerning this, teachers' participation and cooperation; their viewpoint; expertise; and experience were contributing factors as to whether the implementation would succeed or fail. In the end, both administrative efficacy and dedication may have a significant influence on how well IE is implemented.

In the Philippines, out of the projected 444,294 children with special educational needs, only 112,810 were enrolled in 2021 (Romero, 2021). Although this was slightly higher than those who were enrolled in the previous year, it was still lower than the projected number of children with special educational needs. Despite this, the number of pupils with disabilities enrolled decreased by 74% from its pre-pandemic level of 360,879, according to the statistics cited. Other than the unstable enrollment, concern about the number of schools serving as SPED Schools/Centers is challenging the educational system. There are only about 485 public Elementary and 164 public High Schools in the Philippines that serve as SPED Schools/Centers (National Council on Disability Affairs [NCDA], 2023). These numbers are not enough to achieve and sustain the goals of education for LWDs. When considering access to IE as an indicator of success; these data show that an IE in the Philippines needs to be intensified to reach more LWDs/LSEs and provide them equal opportunities to acquire quality education.

Looking at the SHS implementation among regions in the Philippines, DepEd 4-A former Regional Director Diosdado San Antonio stated that CALABARZON was the biggest among the 17 regions in the country that implemented the SHS program (Montemayor, 2018). Hence, their failure could have influenced the nationwide result of the program and that could include the outcome of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities. The said region has only 38 public elementary and 11 public high schools serving as SPED schools where only four elementary and two high schools are in Rizal Province. The figures imply a very minimal number of public SPED Centers throughout the province of Rizal (NCDA, 2023).

Fortunately, policy guidelines for program implementers, stakeholders, and the school community were issued. It comprises the implementation of appropriate

interventions and services for learners with special educational needs at all key stages in public and private schools. So, like elementary and junior high school levels, the SHS envisions access and quality, benefiting from the system that DepEd offers (DepEd, 2023). Thus, this policy (DepEd Order No. 44, s. 2021), assures that learners with disabilities can now be mainstreamed and be given equal possibilities to actively engage in the K–12 Basic Education Program.

In connection to that, issues and concerns like unstable enrollment for the past years and the minimal number of SPED Centers throughout the Philippines clearly attest that IE on Learners with Disabilities usually takes place only in elementary and junior high schools. Hence, it articulates a gap in the implementation of inclusive education for LWDs across all key stages. In addition, it can also be noted that in the general context of inclusive education, the elementary and junior high school levels comprise more Inclusive Education offerings than Senior High School.

Ultimately, it illustrates the importance of research pertaining to identifying and addressing issues and challenges; and discussions about the quality implementation of inclusive education for learners with disabilities especially at the senior high school level that has only been established in less than a decade. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the total quality management (TQM) of IE implementation for LWDs, in public senior high schools in Rizal province as a basis for program enhancement.

The implementation of inclusive education for students with disabilities in the Philippines is regulated by the policies and guidelines outlined in DO 44 s, 2021. Guidelines for Identification and Referral, Assessment Services, Adaptation of the K–12 Curriculum for LWDs, Development of an Individualized Educational Plan (IEP), Resource Room Services, Educational Placement, Program Delivery, and Program Management at the school level are all outlined in the aforementioned policy. Concerning program implementation, organizations around the world recognize Dr. Deming's total quality management, which emphasizes customer satisfaction and continuous improvement, as an effective management strategy (Deming, 2018). As criteria or indicators, the principles of total quality management are implemented in a variety of institutions and organizations.

Shourbagi (2017) proposed that in order to foster a more robust partnership between schools and parents, top-level management should ensure that educators and parents maintain an ongoing dialogue during the planning and execution phases of inclusive education. Furthermore, it is critical that leaders have a comprehensive understanding of the specific activities conducted within their institutions in order to identify potential solutions to the obstacles and constraints (Mittal et al., 2019). Furthermore, total quality management practices have the potential to influence the performance of educators by means of knowledge sharing (Saffar et al. 2020).

Adverse comments were identified, such as schools that implemented TQM to a moderate extent in research and budget allocation (Avila, 2018); and administrators who lacked significant proficiency in TQM when it came to budget allocation and research.

However, it is worth noting that some principals exhibited a deficiency in their comprehension of inclusive education management, which consequently resulted in a failure to adequately support students with special needs in adherence to relevant regulations (Rahmi, et al., 20

Moreover, client satisfaction required an awareness of the school's mission (Bagrova, et al., 2020) and the requirements of its students (Muega, 2016; Al Qahtani, et al., 2015). In the realm of process management, total quality management practices can function as a framework for guidance, particularly in situations where administrators and teachers may experience uncertainty or doubt regarding their own performance in relation to the management of inclusive education for LSENs (Muega, 2016). Similar to other types of organizations, schools are susceptible to inadequate quality control practices (Al-Qahtani et al., 2015).

In comparison to total quality management practices, training enables educators to comprehend instruction prior to practical application; it influences educators' productivity, leading to increased satisfaction (Dziuba, et al., 2020); this is due to the fact that training is the determining factor in employees' perceptions of their own performance; it fosters employee engagement in the learning process; and it facilitates instruction comprehension prior to practical application (Mo, et al., 2022). However, it is worth noting that some educational institutions in a specific province of the Philippines employed instructors with comparatively inadequate training (Masongsong, et al., 2023). This suggested that the efficacy of educators might depend less on their formal education and more on their inherent abilities and pre-existing knowledge.

Likewise, administrators may seek to engage and empower faculty and staff, as research indicates that empowered personnel exhibit greater job satisfaction and performance (Davidescu et al., 2020). This would likely elicit a favorable reaction from stakeholders regarding the execution of the aforementioned initiative.

Additionally, open communication was recommended (Zaman, et al., 2016), and the source of instructors' apprehension regarding the implementation of inclusive education programs should be identified. This may be the result of external factors including inadequate managerial competencies, insufficient knowledge and skills regarding change implementation, communication deficiencies, insufficient employee team building, and insufficient work organization or empowerment (Bugdol, 2020).

Certain educational institutions that had not undergone adequate monitoring and evaluation during the implementation of inclusive education could benefit greatly from the elimination of management by objectives. This would constitute a substantial step toward achieving continuous improvement (Rahmi, et al., 2021).

Likewise, in order to attain a more comprehensive comprehension of the TQM concept, it is imperative to acknowledge the obstacles that impede the implementation of TQM within organizations (Alghamdi, 2016). Obstacles to the implementation of TQM, according to Deming (2018), include a lack of purpose consistency, short-term thinking,

annual performance reviews that fail to account for employee development, job-hopping due to attrition concerns, and the reliance on visible metrics.

Furthermore, a number of studies have highlighted the insufficient application of education and self-improvement strategies. It is recommended that educators participate in seminars and training regarding inclusive education. An observation was made regarding educators who instructed LWDs but deemed themselves unqualified to instruct LSEs due to insufficient training (Allam & Martin, 2021). The same conclusions were drawn: notwithstanding teachers' personal expertise, they required a variety of current special education seminars, workshops, and training to equip them with the necessary skills to manage students' behavior and to impart lessons to their mainstream counterparts (Ecoben, 2016).

Finally, to increase the level of implementation of inclusive education for students with special educational needs, administrators, teachers, and parents must examine possible effective approaches and best practices, according to a number of studies, in order to foster a workplace transformation that requires the participation of all employees (Pajarillo, 2019).

Research Questions

The study assessed the total quality management (TQM) of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities in the division of Rizal for a basis for program enhancement. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How did the school administrators, teachers, and parents rate the TQM of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities in the division of Rizal in terms of:
 - 1.1. commitment of top management;
 - 1.2. customer focus;
 - 1.3. process management;
 - 1.4. instituting training on the job;
 - 1.5. instituting leadership;
 - 1.6. driving-out fear;
 - 1.7. eliminating management by objectives;
 - 1.8. removing barriers to pride of workmanship;
 - 1.9. implementing education and self-improvement for everyone; and
 - 1.10. making transformation a job for everyone at work?
2. Is there any significant difference in the assessment of TQM of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities among administrators, teachers, and parents in terms of the above-mentioned key elements of TQM?
3. What were the challenges encountered by the school administrator respondents and teacher respondents in regard to the implementation of inclusive education for learners with disabilities?

Hypothesis

Given the stated research question, the null hypothesis was tested:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the assessment of TQM of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities among the administrators, teachers, and parents in terms of the principles of TQM: commitment of the top management; customer focus; process management; instituting training on the job; instituting leadership; driving-out fear; eliminating management by objectives; removing barriers to pride of workmanship; implementing education and self- improvement for everyone; and making transformation a job for everyone at work.

METHODOLOGY

In the survey, eight schools were included. Eight administrators, one hundred fourteen (114) instructors, and forty-nine (49) parents comprised the population, for a grand total of one hundred seventy-one (171) individuals. The researcher gathered data from a sample size of one hundred and fifty-two (152) respondents. . They were the administrators, senior high school teachers, and parents. The administrators are principals who have identified students with disabilities. They are ones who bear responsibility for the implementation and stringent observance of the provisions outlined in DO 44, section 2021. The Seniors High School Teachers are general education teachers (as per DO 44, s. 2021) who instruct classes with identified students who have special education requirements and are affiliated with eight schools in the Division of Rizal. They are regarded as the primary agents of inclusive education implementation. Lastly, parents as the legal custodians or parents of students who have been identified as having special educational needs or disabilities. By actively participating as members of the school community, they gain a more comprehensive comprehension of the condition of each student.

As a foundation for program improvement, the purpose of the study was to evaluate the comprehensive quality management (TQM) of inclusive education implementation for students with disabilities in the division of Rizal. In order to respond to the study's problem statement and research inquiries, the investigators employed a questionnaire that they had developed using both paper and pen and Google Forms.

Three specialists validated the questionnaire, which was then translated into Filipino so that it could be readily understood by the parents. The initial segment of the survey involved profiling, which aimed to ascertain the respondents' professional status as parents, educators, or administrators. The second component comprised a 50-item Likert scale that utilized the ten principles of TQM as indicators to assess the degree of implementation of inclusive education for students with disabilities. Five indicators were designated for each TQM principle. Items 1-5 addressed the commitment of top

management, while Items 6-10 addressed process management. Items 11-15 dealt with process management. Items 16 to 20 addressed the implementation of on-the-job training, items 21-25 addressed leadership implementation, items 26-30 addressed driving out fear, items 31-35 addressed eliminating management by objectives, items 36-40 addressed removing barriers to pride in workmanship, items 41-45 addressed implementing education and self-improvement for all, and items 46-50 addressed making transformation a job for every employee.

Ten items comprised the third section, which assessed the degree to which respondents agreed with each of the obstacles associated with instituting inclusive education for LWDs. The participation of principals and instructors was limited to the third section of the survey.

After conducting pilot tests of the instrument in public senior high schools in Quezon City, the collected data were subjected to reliability analysis. With a reliability coefficient of 0.984, the TQM instrument demonstrates exceptional internal consistency reliability. Ultimately, the questionnaire pertaining to the Challenges Encountered in the TQM implementation possesses a reliability coefficient of 0.929. This value signifies that each item possesses exceptional internal consistency reliability.

The researcher coordinated her data-collection process, procedure, and actions with her advisor in order to obtain permission, conduct surveillance, and take appropriate actions. The researcher approached the Superintendent of the Schools Division for authorization to conduct an investigation in the Division of Rizal's Public Senior High Schools. The researcher developed a questionnaire while awaiting the permit and subsequently sought the validation of three specialists in the domain of inclusive education, with a specific focus on the SNED Program. After confirming the questionnaire's validity, the investigators approached the University Research Ethics Center (UREC) for approval to proceed with the study. Upon receiving approval from the UREC to conduct the study, the researcher approached the Institution for Data and Statistical Analysis (IDSA) for statistical services. The researcher was then recommended by the IDSA to the University Statistician.

Subsequently, the researcher approached the Schools Division Superintendent of Quezon City for authorization to administer the pilot testing in a subset of senior high schools located in QC. The researcher performed a pilot test and forwarded the data to the statistician in order to assess the reliability of the instrument. As soon as the statistician confirmed the instrument's reliability, the researcher arranged with the Division Coordinator for the SNED program to request the names of schools that had identified students with disabilities. The researcher then collected data in the Division of Rizal with the superintendent of the school division's approval.

The researcher solicited permission from the school principals to conduct a study in their respective institutions by composing a letter that detailed the purpose and scope of the research. The researcher coordinated with the senior high school's assistant principal, coordinator, or adviser of each LWD to provide an explanation of the study's

scope and purpose once the principal granted permission for data collection. The researcher requested the assistance of the relevant school personnel in disseminating the questionnaires to the parents of identified LWD. The questionnaires were hardcopy and written in Filipino. Additionally, the researcher provided a QR Code for a research questionnaire, in the event that a parent preferred to complete it via Google Forms.

The researcher then requested that administrators and educators to complete the questionnaire (in English). The respondents were able to access the Google Form via QR Code or printed copy. The researcher visited each participating school and utilized text messaging, messenger, phone calls, and in-person visits to ensure that the necessary number of responses were collected. The entirety of the responses was collected within a single month. The collected data were subsequently forwarded to the university statistician for statistical analysis by the researcher.

The descriptive statistic used by the researcher was the median. This was used to determine how the administrators, teachers, and parents rated the total quality management of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities in division of Rizal in terms of principles of TQM; what the challenges encountered by the administrators and teachers in regard to implementation of inclusive education for learners with disabilities. In addition, to determine whether to reject or fail to reject the null hypothesis, "There is no significant difference in the assessment of administrators, teachers, and parents on the TQM of inclusive education implementation for learners with disabilities in terms of the above-mentioned key elements of TQM", the researcher used inferential statistic under nonparametric test, Kruskal-Wallis H- Test, a non-parametric equivalent to the One-Way ANOVA. It was because the independent data was categorical and the dependent data was ordinal/continuous. The Likert scale is ordinal data because the items have a clear rank order, but do not have an even distribution.

RESULTS

To ensure the quality and efficacy of an organization, adherence to certain fundamental principles of total quality management is imperative. Production of cost-effective, high-quality commodities and services, cost reduction, long-term demand, and efficiency are the principal objectives of management.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Commitment of Top Management

The commitment of Top Management- school administrator, is essential for establishing a consistent goal for bettering goods and services. It discusses establishing a goal and exhibiting dedication.

Table 1

Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Commitment of Top Management

Commitment of Top Management	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our school promotes the inclusion of LWDs with mild to moderate disabilities in the regular classroom or mainstreamed classes by providing programs and services to our LWDs.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2. Our school involves teachers and parents in planning for LWDs through the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and/or Annual Implementation Plan (AIP).	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3. Our school is committed in ensuring constant improvement toward a quality of service for LWDs such as innovation in allocating resources for long-term planning including research and education; and having school guidelines to follow in implementing inclusive education for learners with disabilities.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4. Our school communicates the vision, aims, goals, and objectives with the aim of constant improvement on the implementation of inclusive education for learners with disabilities to the parents, community, and other stakeholders like LGU, etc.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school is committed to carrying out activities with the aim of successful and sustainable implementation of inclusive education for LWDs in terms of leadership.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)*

1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*

2.51 – 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*

3.51 – 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*

4.51 – 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

In terms of the commitment of top management, the table details the administrators', teachers', and parents' evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation in public senior high schools in Rizal.

The median score for each indicator is 4.00, which is interpreted verbally as indicating a high level of implementation. The administrators obtained the highest median score of 4.50 among the three categories, further suggesting a substantial degree of implementation.

This suggests that the administrators believe that they are implementing inclusive education in accordance with TQM principles and that they comply with Deped Order 44, section 2021, which underscored the obligation of school principals to rigorously enforce its stipulations.

Furthermore, the feedback from the educators and the guardians suggests that the upper management is committed to instituting inclusive education for students with disabilities; however, further progress is required to attain an exceptionally high level of implementation. This implies that ongoing collaboration between the parents and the schools can be strengthened through the inclusion of the teachers and the parents in the planning and execution of inclusive education for students with disabilities (Shourbagi, 2017).

In addition, the researcher asserts that the leaders must have a comprehensive understanding of the specific activities conducted within their educational institutions in order to identify potential alternatives (Mittal, et al., 2019) and resolutions to the obstacles and constraints. Furthermore, by exchanging knowledge, TQM practices can have an effect on the efficacy of educators (Saffar, et al. 2020).

Conversely, the findings of this study contradicted those of Avila (2018), which found that schools implemented TQM to a moderate degree with regard to budget allocation and research, and that administrators lacked significant proficiency in TQM application with regard to budget allocation and research. Furthermore, according to research by Rahmi, et al. (2020), some principals continued to lack a comprehensive understanding of inclusive education management and exhibited a lack of dedication to servicing students with special needs in compliance with relevant regulations.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Customer-Focus

Customer-Focus is an action of school administrators and teachers, which entails embracing a new worldview; waking up to the task, taking on leadership roles, and learning duties in order to bring about change by clearly communicating the mission to all stakeholders.

Table 2

Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Customer Focus

Customer Focus	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our school creates mechanisms to determine the needs necessary in implementing and sustaining inclusive education for learners with disabilities based on our school's context.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2. Our school creates a community that has a positive attitude or acceptance toward inclusive education for LSENS.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3. Our school ensures that the basic materials like learning resources that are developed and utilized by teachers in implementing inclusive education for LSENS correspond with the goals and objectives of our school for the program.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4. Guidelines and policies are explained to the teachers and staff to avoid certain levels of mistake in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school ensures to provide the teachers and staff knowledge along with the implementation of inclusive education for learners with disabilities or special educational needs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)*

1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*

2.51 - 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*

3.51 - 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*

4.51 - 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

In terms of customer focus, Table 2 details the evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation in public senior high schools in Rizal by the administrators, teachers, and parents.

Each of the five indicators received an identical median response of 4.00, indicating a substantial degree of customer-centric implementation. Furthermore, with identical median scores of 4.00, the administrators, teachers, and parents all demonstrated a substantial degree of implementation. This demonstrates that the schools have successfully implemented inclusive education by attending to the requirements of the students; thus, it substantiated the schools' compliance with TQM and DO 44, s. 2021. It suggests that educational institutions placed equal emphasis on customer satisfaction and program implementation.

Thus, the administrators, teachers, and parents noted that the inclusive education implementers had a profound understanding of the school's mission (Bagrova, et al., 2020) and had effectively prioritized the needs of the students. This is supported by the findings of Muega's (2016) study, in which the methodologies utilized by inclusive education participants were determined by the academic requirements of their pupils. However, this finding contradicts the research conducted by Al Qahtani, et al. (2015), which demonstrated that certain organizations neglected to prioritize the needs of their customers.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Process Management

Process Management is about ceasing reliance on mass inspection by school leaders, for quality assurance. It can be eliminated by incorporating quality into the product from the start.

Table 3
Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Process Management

Process Management	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1.Our school makes use of a tool or instrument that is used to plan and take actions about the limitations and challenges in terms of the quality of implementation of inclusive education for LSEs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2.Our school has established a system of communication in a way of discussion which helps us understand the context and process of achieving quality in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3.Our school identifies current and long-term issues pertaining to the implementation of inclusive education for LSEs to support each member of the school and understand their challenges.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4.Our school creates and sustains quality that is considered a process of implementing inclusive education for LWDs by continuous improvement of school guidelines for clarity and ease.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school is determined to perform corrective actions to ensure quality and continuous improvement in the implementation of inclusive education for LSEs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

Overall Median	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
1.00 - 1.50	<i>Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)</i>				
1.51 - 2.50	<i>Low Level of Implementation (LLI)</i>				
2.51 – 3.50	<i>Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)</i>				
3.51 – 4.50	<i>High Level of Implementation (HLI)</i>				
4.51 – 5.00	<i>Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)</i>				

In terms of process management, Table 3 details the evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation by the administrators, teachers, and parents in the public senior high schools in Rizal.

All indicators, including the following: utilizing a tool or instrument to strategize and execute actions regarding the constraints and difficulties associated with the quality of inclusive education implementation for children with special educational needs and disabilities (LSEN); establishing a communication system that facilitates dialogue to comprehend the context and procedure for attaining quality in inclusive education implementation for individuals with disabilities; and identifying present and future concerns related to the implementation of inclusive education for LWDs received a median score of 4.00. Furthermore, with an equal median score of 4.00, the administrators, teachers, and parents all expressed the belief that inclusive education for students with disabilities was effectively implemented.

Moreover, this implies that the parents themselves perceived a considerable degree of execution with regard to process management; the administrators and the teachers, on the other hand, might harbor skepticism or uncertainty regarding their own performance in regard to the process management of inclusive education for LSENs (Muega, 2016). However, this result is superior to that of Al-Qahtani, et al. (2015), which revealed that some organizations had inadequate process management-based quality control implementation. Furthermore, this suggests that, similar to other establishments, there are prospects for enhancing the implementation process (Bagrova et al., 2021). With this in mind, educational institutions can strive for a certain degree of inclusive education implementation for LSENs by consistently enhancing their services.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Instituting Training on the Job

Instituting training on the job highlights the value of employee training, including how it boosts output and gives teachers the chance to grow their knowledge and abilities so they can collaborate more effectively.

Table 4

Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Instituting Training on the Job

Instituting Training on the Job	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1.Our school capacitates teachers through trainings about inclusive education for LSEs or LWDs to allow us to understand instructions before being exposed to implementing inclusive education.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2.Our school facilitates teachers' skills renewal, increases professionalism, and increases employee commitment and satisfaction to the organization in terms of implementing inclusive education for LWDs and LSEs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3.Our school conducts teacher induction programs, INSETs, LAC sessions, conferences, and community engagement to enhance our capacity and productivity to implement inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4.Our school provides the teachers with opportunities to engage in more efficient teamwork and learn from colleagues through trainings on inclusive education for LSEs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5.Our school encourages teachers to recognize gaps and variations when it comes to implementing Inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

- 1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)*
- 1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*
- 2.51 – 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*
- 3.51 – 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*
- 4.51 – 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

In terms of instituting on-the-job training, Table 4 details the evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation by the administrators, teachers, and parents in the public senior high schools in Rizal.

The median response for each indicator was 4.00, which is interpreted verbally as a significant level of implementation. Despite the finding indicating progress in program implementation through the incorporation of on-the-job training, it remains a favorable assessment in comparison to the research conducted by Masongsong, et al. (2023), which identified a comparatively inadequate level of training among a subset of teachers in a specific Philippine province and suggested that their efficacy might stem from innate abilities and pre-existing knowledge rather than formal education.

Furthermore, the outcome suggests that there is scope for enhancement in order to achieve an exceptionally high standard of program implementation with regard to on-

the-job training. This assertion is corroborated by the research conducted by Mo, et al. (2022), which found that the training specifically tailored for employees was the primary determinant in shaping their perception of performance. Training facilitates instructors' comprehension of instructions prior to their practical implementation, and it influences their efficiency, culminating in increased job satisfaction (Dziuba, et al., 2020).

Therefore, quality management training plays a pivotal role in fostering employee engagement in the process (Mo, et al., 2022); this is due to the belief that it enhances employees' task performance capabilities (Mohammed, 2016). This is corroborated by Muega's (2016) observation that lack of training was one of the most significant obstacles to implementing inclusive education.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Instituting Leadership

Instituting leadership exemplifies the goal of school administrators in terms of supervision, which is to support improved performance. One effective way for school leaders to influence employee attitudes and behaviors—such as time theft and cynicism—is through leadership.

Table 5
Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Instituting Training on the Job

Instituting Leadership	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1.The school leader displays a kind of leadership that helps me reach my full potential and not just focus on deadlines and measures when it comes to implementing inclusive education for LWDs or LSEns.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
1.The school leader displays a kind of leadership performing instructional supervision and management of learning delivery in inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2. The school leader allows teachers to be empowered toward implementing inclusive education for LSEns.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3. The school leader has worked on sources of improvement and the process of quality services in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4.The school leader provides teachers with an inspiring vision, strategic directions, and values that guide them in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

1.00 - 1.50 Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)

1.51 - 2.50 Low Level of Implementation (LLI)

2.51 – 3.50 Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)

3.51 – 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*
 4.51 – 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

Table 5 displays the administrators', teachers', and parents' evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation in the public senior high schools in Rizal with regard instituting leadership.

The median response for all indicators was 4.00, which corresponds to a high level of implementation as determined by its verbal interpretation. Furthermore, the median responses of all three groups demonstrate a substantial degree of implementation. This suggests that, in order to achieve a higher level of implementation, the schools' process of inclusive education for students with special educational needs could be enhanced in the area of leadership.

At the end, administrators may seek to engage and empower faculty and staff; since empowered personnel report greater job contentment and productivity (Davidescu, et al., 2020), this could generate a favorable reaction to the program's implementation.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Driving-Out Fear

Driving-Out Fear promotes better communication and other strategies to eradicate fear across the organization, which is essential for everyone to operate more efficiently and successfully for the business.

Table 6
 Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Driving-Out Fear

Driving- Out Fear	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our school encourages teachers to engage in a two-way communication and other means, to express ideas and ask questions without fear or hesitation in implementing inclusive education for learners with disabilities or special educational needs.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2. Our school doesn't make us feel intimidated when we are being corrected.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3. Our school motivates teachers to not dwell on fear about new knowledge, and embrace quality in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4. Our school helps teachers develop cooperation, teamwork, and constant improvement to serve the best interest of the school in implementing inclusive education for LSEs.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

5. Our school helps teachers to not fear committing mistake and asking questions to understand better the reasons of such process in implementation of inclusive education for LWDs.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)*

1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*

2.51 – 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*

3.51 – 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*

4.51 – 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

In terms of driving-out fear, Table 7 details the evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation by the administrators, teachers, and parents in the public senior high schools in Rizal.

All indicators (promoting active teacher participation in two-way communication and other avenues, encouraging fearless expression of ideas and inquiry, and fostering an environment where teachers feel comfortable seeking corrections) contribute to the following: facilitating inclusive education for learners with disabilities or special educational needs; encouraging teachers to embrace quality rather than fixate on apprehension regarding new information; assisting teachers in developing cooperative skills.

Furthermore, the administrators obtained the highest median score of 5.00, indicating a very high level of implementation, among the three categories. Teachers and parents, on the other hand, received a median score of 4.00, indicating a high level of implementation. This suggests that the responses of educators and guardians were comparatively less fear-inducing than the evaluation of implementation by the administrators. This underscores the necessity of identifying the origin of the instructors' apprehension prior to implementing inclusive education programs.

This may be the result of external factors including inadequate managerial competencies, insufficient knowledge and skills regarding change implementation, communication deficiencies, insufficient employee team building, and insufficient work organization or empowerment (Bugdol, 2020). In this regard, Zaman, et al. (2016) suggest that open communication may facilitate TQM in the education sector.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Eliminating Management by Objectives

Eliminating Management by Objectives can be achieved by doing away with arbitrary numerical targets and placing an emphasis on quality rather than quantity.

Table 7

Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Eliminating Management by Objectives

Eliminating Management by Objectives	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our school performs monitoring and evaluation of the process of implementation of inclusive education for LWDs to identify how to serve better the learners for continuous improvement.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2. Our school utilizes an evaluation system to determine personnel that needs special help or attention when it comes to implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
3. Our school uses a Client Satisfaction Survey or Tools to measure the school's processes toward inclusive education.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4. Our school's processes included in the implementation of inclusive education for LSENs are posted through their respective websites or in the form of published materials such as handbooks written either in English or Filipino or in the local dialect.	4.50	4.00	5.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school has a strong and fair reward system in order to motivate the teachers to implement inclusive education for LWDs.	4.50	4.00	5.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)*

1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*

2.51 – 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*

3.51 – 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*

4.51 – 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

In terms of eliminating management by objectives, Table 8 details the evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation in the public senior high schools in Rizal by the administrators, teachers, and parents.

The median response for each indicator is 4.00, indicating a high level of implementation. In comparison to the other two categories, the administrators received the highest median response of 5.00, signifying an exceptionally high degree of implementation. Conversely, the teachers and the parents obtained a median response of 4.00, signifying a high degree of implementation.

However, the median response from the parents for indicators four and five was 5.00. This result indicates that the median response of teachers regarding the elimination of management by objectives was lower than the median response of administrators regarding implementation. This indicates that the administrators may be deficient in TQM practices pertaining to the elimination of management by objectives in inclusive education implementation. This is comparable to the findings of Rahmi, et al. (2021), who discovered that certain educational institutions had not been adequately monitored and evaluated during the implementation of inclusive education, a crucial step toward ensuring ongoing progress.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Removing Barriers to Pride in Workmanship

Removing Barriers to Pride in Workmanship is about maintaining performance through the development of school administrators and teachers; and removing barriers to attain pride in workmanship and job- satisfaction.

Table 8
Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Removing Barriers to Pride in Workmanship

Removing Barriers to Pride in Workmanship	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Every teacher in our school is considered a unique and valuable part of the human resource implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	5.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	HLI
2. Our school measures the performance of each committee/department in implementing inclusive education for LSEs, giving importance for general as a whole rather than generating individual performance of teachers.	5.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	HLI
3. My skills are built to make me more adaptable to change, do a good job and improvements, and take a pride of my work in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4. Our school has an established system's code of ethics that outlines guidelines on inclusive education for LSEs, that all teachers adhere to in the performance of their work	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school helps teachers to have a feeling of satisfaction in implementing inclusive education for LWDs.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

- 1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI)*
- 1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*
- 2.51 – 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*
- 3.51 – 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*

4.51 – 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

In terms of removing obstacles to workmanship pride, Table 8 details the evaluation of the TQM of inclusive education implementation by the administrators, teachers, and parents in the public senior high schools in Rizal.

With a median score of 4.00, all indicators are verbally interpreted as indicating a high level of implementation. This finding contradicts the results of Avila's (2018) study, which indicated only a moderate level of TQM practice, which may impede the successful implementation of inclusive education.

The administrators achieved a median score of 5.00, that signify an exceptionally high degree of implementation. In contrast, the instructors and the parents scored a median of 4.00, which can only be interpreted verbally as a high degree of implementation. In contrast, the median response from parents for indicators 1 and 2 was 5.00, which is interpreted verbally as a "very high level of implementation." These results indicate that the median response of the educators regarding the elimination of obstacles to pride in workmanship was lower than the response of the administrators regarding implementation. This suggests that the administrators implementing inclusive education may be deficient in TQM practices for eradicating obstacles to pride in workmanship.

It is critical to bear in mind that the development and implementation of TQM necessitate additional exertion and may face obstacles. In order to enhance comprehension of the TQM concept, it is imperative to acknowledge the obstacles that impede the implementation of TQM within organizations (Alghamdi, 2016). Obstacles to the implementation of TQM, according to Dr. Deming (2018), include a lack of purpose consistency, short-term thinking, annual performance reviews that fail to account for employee development, job-hopping due to attrition concerns, and the reliance on visible metrics.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Implementing Education and Self-Improvement

Implementing Education and Self-Improvement involves the notion that management must encourage continuous learning and education in order for businesses to stay ahead of their rivals.

Table 9
Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Implementing Education and Self-Improvement

Implementing Education and Self-Improvement	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. The school utilizes the Individual Education Plan and individual transition	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

plan as bases for monitoring the progress of evaluation of learners with disabilities to unlock the full potential of students as a modern management strategy.					
2. The school ensures that data on LWDs are updated, correct, and properly encoded in the LIS and uses school data in planning for and allocating resources for the school	5.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	HLI
3. The school provides learners with disabilities with different delivery modalities or options; thus, instructional delivery shall be based on the residential distance from the school, family structure, health condition, and/or other factors to be determined by the school officials.	5.00	4.00	4.50	4.00	HLI
4. Our school establishes a clear referral system with partners that promote collaborative management of resources and provisions of appropriate support and interventions for LWDs and Generate support for learners' health, medical, and overall welfare.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school strengthens the practice of giving formative assessments; providing modifications and adaptations, contextualization in the curriculum; and giving summative assessments to LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

- 1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI):*
 1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*
 2.51 - 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*
 3.51 - 4.50 *High Level of Implementation (HLI)*
 4.51 - 5.00 *Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)*

The evaluation of the quality of inclusive education implementation by the administrators, instructors, and parents in the public senior high schools in Rizal with regard to self-improvement and education implementation is detailed in Table 9.

The verbal interpretation of all indicators reaching a median of 4.00 indicates a high level of implementation. The administrators achieved a median score of 5.00, signifying an exceptionally high degree of implementation, among the three categories. In contrast, the teachers and the parents obtained a median score of 4.00, which can only be interpreted verbally as a high degree of implementation. However, the median responses of the parents regarding indicators 2 (ensuring that data on learning disabilities are accurate, current, and appropriately encoded in the Learning Information System and utilizing school data for resource allocation and planning) and 3 (offering diverse instructional delivery modalities or alternatives for learners with disabilities; thus, instructional delivery shall be determined by factors such as family structure, health condition, residential distance from the school, and other such determinants as determined by the school).

This result indicates that the educators perceived a deficiency in their ability to implement this principle, indicating that they would benefit from more intensive seminars

and training regarding inclusive education. This is corroborated by the research conducted by Allam and Martin (2021), which revealed that certain educators instructing LWDs lacked training and believed themselves unqualified to instruct LSEs.

The identical results were reported in Ecoben's (2016) study, which indicated that teachers, despite possessing personal expertise, still required a range of current special education seminars, workshops, and training to effectively manage the behavior of their students and impart effective teaching strategies to their mainstream counterparts.

Assessment of School Administrators, Teachers, and Parents from Public Senior High Schools in the Division of Rizal on Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Making Transformation a Job for Everyone at Work

Making Transformation a Job for Everyone at Work relates to the goal of the school administration to develop a thorough action plan for high-quality assignments. This is a thorough message for any firm looking to ensure quality.

Table 10
Respondents' Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation in Terms of Making Transformation a Job for Everyone at Work

Making Transformation a Job for Everyone at Work	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Median Response of Parents	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Our school assesses learners with disabilities not only to clearly establish the goals for their learning and development areas but also to continually monitor their progress in all domains of development (cognitive, socio-emotional, physical, motor, and moral-spiritual domains).	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
2. Our school offers Resource Room Services intended for specific instructional interventions and other related services outside of general education classrooms; tutorial and remedial sessions for LWDs; and assessment services for LWDs educational placement and referrals.	5.00	4.00	4.50	4.00	HLI
3. Our school utilizes school data in planning and allocating resources for the school implementation of inclusive education for LSEs.	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
4. Our school establishes and sustains strong partnerships with families, government agencies, local government units, non-government organizations, and medical and allied medical institutions by coordinating with them and ensuring that learners and families are informed of the implementation of inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
5. Our school applies approaches to transform people and culture within our organization to achieve effective implementation of inclusive education for LWDs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI
Overall Median	4.50	4.00	4.00	4.00	HLI

1.00 - 1.50 *Very Low Level of Implementation (VLLI):*
 1.51 - 2.50 *Low Level of Implementation (LLI)*
 2.51 – 3.50 *Moderate Level of Implementation (MLI)*

3.51 – 4.50 High Level of Implementation (HLI)
 4.51 – 5.00 Very High Level of Implementation (VHLI)

The evaluation of the quality of inclusive education implementation by the administrators, teachers, and parents in the public senior high schools in Rizal with regard to transforming the work environment for all is detailed in Table 10.

The verbal interpretation of all five indicators yielded a median score of 4.00, indicating a significant degree of implementation. In contrast, the administrators obtained a median response of 5.00, indicating a very high level of implementation, for indicators 1 and 2. Indicator 1 requires administrators to assess learners with disabilities in order to establish clear goals for their learning and development areas and to continuously monitor their progress across all domains of development; Indicator 2 pertains to the provision of Resource Room Services, which are designed to facilitate specific instructional interventions and other related services beyond the confines of general education classrooms. The median response from parents was 4.50, indicating a high level of implementation for indicator 2.

The administrators received the highest median response of 4.50, indicating a high level of implementation based on verbal interpretation, among the three categories. Teachers and parents, on the other hand, only received a median response of 4.00, which also indicates a high level of implementation.

The findings highlight the necessity to examine potential efficacious strategies and exemplary practices, such as those delineated by Pajarillo (2019), which involve input from administrators, teachers, and parents. In order to enhance the standard of inclusive education implementation for students with special educational needs, it is imperative that this transformation becomes a collective responsibility within the workplace.

Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation Among the Respondents

The effective implementation of an inclusive education program—which aims to ensure quality, relevance, and responsive special education—requires the active participation of families and strong support from various administrative positions and stakeholders. Testing the significant difference of the responses of school administrators, teachers, and parents, based on such parameters would provide findings and conclusions on the principles that needs to be improved.

Table 11
 Kruskal Wallis H- Test: Difference in the Assessment of TQM of Inclusive Education Implementation Among the Respondents

Principle	Group	Mean Rank	K-	P-value	Decision	Remarks
1. Commitment of Top- Management	Administrators	81.00	0.176	0.916	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	75.84				
	Parents	77.80				

2. Customer- Focus	Administrators	70.63	3.531	0.171	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	73.86				
	Parents	88.12				
3. Process Management	Administrators	90.94	4.467	0.107	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	72.84				
	Parents	86.57				
4. Instituting Training on the Job	Administrators	78.13	1.409	0.494	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	74.44				
	Parents	83.90				
5. Instituting Leadership	Administrators	81.00	0.129	0.937	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	76.01				
	Parents	77.17				
6. Driving- Out Fear	Administrators	102.00	4.193	0.123	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	73.68				
	Parents	80.43				
7. Eliminating Management by Objectives	Administrators	104.00	5.572	0.062	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	72.76				
	Parents	83.37				
8. Removing Barriers to Pride in Workmanship	Administrators	102.13	6.623	0.036	Reject H_0	Difference is significant
	Teachers	72.05				
	Parents	86.58				
9. Implementing Education and Self-Improvement	Administrators	103.88	7.841	0.020	Reject H_0	Difference is significant
	Teachers	71.79				
	Parents	87.08				
10. Making Transformation a Job for Everyone at Work	Administrators	95.50	4.490	0.106	Failed to Reject H_0	Difference is not significant
	Teachers	72.82				
	Parents	85.40				

If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject H_0 , otherwise failed to reject H_0 .

The table shows the difference in the assessment of the administrators, teachers, and parents about TQM of inclusive education implementation in terms of its principles.

In the first principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 81.00; followed by the parents at 77.80; and the teachers at 75.84. The observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers and the parents. With the K-statistic of 0.716, the computed p-value is 0.916; the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to the commitment of the top management.

In the second principle, the parents got the highest mean rank of 88.12; followed by the teachers at 73.86; and then the administrators at 70.63. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of parents tends to be higher than those of the administrators and teachers. With the K-statistic of 0.531, the computed p-value is 0.171 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of the administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to customer focus.

In the third principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 90.94; followed by parents at 86.57; and then teachers at 72.84. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers and parents. With the K-statistic of 4.467, the computed p-value is 0.107 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to process management.

In the fourth principle, the parents got the highest mean rank of 83.90; followed by the administrators at 78.13; and then the teachers at 74.44. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tend to be higher than those of the teachers and parents. With the K-statistic of 1.409, the computed p-value is 0.494 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to instituting training.

In the fifth principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 81.00; followed by the parents at 77.17; and then the teachers at 76.01. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers and parents. With the K-statistic of 0.129, the computed p-value is 0.937 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to adopting and instituting leadership.

In the sixth principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 102.00; followed by the parents at 80.43; and then the teachers at 73.68. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers and parents. With the K-statistic of 4.193, the computed p-value is 0.123 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to driving-out fear.

In the seventh principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 104.00; followed by the parents at 83.37; and then the teachers at 72.76. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers and parents. With the K-statistic of 5.572, the computed p-value is 0.062 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to Eliminating Management by Objectives.

However, with the K-statistic of 6.623, the computed p-value is 0.036 which is less than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference on the assessments of the administrators, the teachers, and the parents when it comes to removing barriers to pride in workmanship. In addition, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 102.13; while the teachers got the lowest

mean rank of 72.05. This infers that even though the administrators rated the implementation of IE higher; the teachers' insights of implementation are lower.

It infers that the administrators may be lacking TQM practices on removing barriers to pride in workmanship in inclusive education implementation; and since the teachers are basically the implementers of IE (DO 44, s. 2021) on the ground, they understand and experience the challenges in implementing IE; especially when there were instances that the teachers were the only ones who searched ways to involve the parents in the school activities (Rahmi, et. al, 2020).

All stakeholders have a prominent role to play in an educational institution (Hoque, et. al, 2017); however, there are still principals who do not fully understand inclusive education management, provide motivation to teachers, collaborate with students with special needs, and lack of commitment in serving LWDs (Rahmi, et. al, 2020) that serve as barriers of implementing IE. It is important to remember that implementing and developing TQM requires more effort and it may encounter some barriers. To get a better understanding of the TQM concept, it is necessary to realize the barriers that stand in the way of pursuing TQM in organizations (Alghamdi, 2016).

Dr. Deming (2018) had mentioned that the barriers to TQM implementation include the lack of constancy of purpose, short-term thinking, and the assessment of employees' performance by annual review, job-hopping (e.g., turnover issues), and the use of visible figures. Acceptance of the facts and expectations are always changing, the organization must adapt and respond to those changes. That way, the strategy of TQM which concentrates on enhancing customer satisfaction levels would easily be recognized and would directly improve organizational performance. Ultimately, leadership commitment is considered a key element for guaranteeing the successful removal of barriers in the implementation of TQM practices at organizations (N. Alauddin, 2020).

Moreover, with the K-statistic of 7.841, the computed p-value is 0.020 which is less than the level of significance (0.05), the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant difference in the assessments of the administrators, the teachers, and the parents when it comes to Implementing education and self-improvement for everyone. In the ninth principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 103.88; and the teachers got the lowest mean rank of 71.79. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers.

This infers that the teachers viewed the implementation in terms of education and self-improvement at a lower level than that of the administrators. Employees' performance is affected by the TQM practices imposed by the school leader (Safar, et al, 2020). It is important that the school leader communicates the activities to teachers, gives the group direction, organizes members' activities; and maintains uniformity to accomplish the goals (Ibrahim, et. al, 2019). It is highly suggested that the administrators should actively participate in the implementation of TQM for students' academic progress (Kakingo, et. al, 2021).

Additionally, teachers are basically the implementers of inclusive education in the teaching and learning context. Therefore, to effectively achieve the goal of inclusion, teachers need thorough training to have knowledge and expertise on how to properly accommodate LSN in their classes, assuage their reservations, and respond positively to specific education (Quinones, 2022).

Finally, in the tenth principle, the administrators got the highest mean rank of 95.50; followed by the parents at 85.40; and then the teachers at 72.82. This implies that the observation of responses in the group of administrators tends to be higher than those of the teachers and parents. With the K-statistic of 4.490, the computed p-value is 0.106 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05); the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no significant difference in the assessments of the administrators, teachers, and parents when it comes to making transformation a job for everyone at work.

Given the significant differences in assessment in Principles 8 and 9, the administrators' group responses evidently had the highest mean rank, while the teachers had the lowest. Among three groups, the teachers also appeared to have the most number of indicators with only high level implementation instead of very high.

Assessment of Challenges Encountered by the School Administrators and Teachers Regarding to Inclusive Education Implementation

In order to attain a more comprehensive comprehension of the TQM concept, it is imperative to acknowledge the obstacles that impede the implementation of TQM within organizations.

Table 12
Assessment of Challenges Encountered by the School Administrators and Teachers Regarding Inclusive Education Implementation

Challenges In Regards to Inclusive Education Implementation	Median Response of Administrators	Median Response of Teachers	Overall Median	Verbal Interpretation
1. Lack of training of general education teachers on dealing with learners with disabilities and mainstreaming them.	3.00	4.00	4.00	Very Challenging
2. Lack of training in the learning process/ deliveries and contextualizing learning materials depending on the needs of learners with disabilities.	2.50	4.00	4.00	Very Challenging
3. Lack of support from higher officials	2.00	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging
4. Lack of support from LGUs	2.00	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging

5. Lack of awareness, support, and participation from parents/ guardians toward assessing learners' special education needs and mainstreaming learners with disabilities	2.50	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging
6. Limited interventions and services at the school level	2.50	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging
7. Unclear implementation down to classroom level	2.00	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging
8. Lack of initiatives in enhancing community awareness and relationship	2.50	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging
9. Lack of physical facilities and equipment	2.00	4.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging
10. Poor monitoring and evaluation process	2.00	3.00	3.00	Moderately Challenging

- 1.00 - 1.50 *Not at All Challenging*
 1.51 - 2.50 *Slightly Challenging*
 2.51 – 3.50 *Moderately Challenging*
 3.51 – 4.50 *Very Challenging*
 4.51 – 5.00 *Extremely Challenging*

The table presents an evaluation of the obstacles that school administrators and instructors in public senior high schools in the province of Rizal have encountered in implementing inclusive education.

Regarding the inadequate preparation of general education teachers to effectively support and integrate students with disabilities into mainstream settings, administrators received an average rating of 3.00, which was interpreted verbally as moderately challenging. On the other hand, teachers received a rating of 4.00, which was interpreted verbally as extremely challenging. The aggregate median score was 4, which signifies a high degree of difficulty. This result is consistent with the outcomes reported in the research conducted by Allam (2021), Ecoben (2019), Gaytos (2020), Quinones (2022), and Pedrigal (2019), which unveiled the difficulties and obstacles resulting from inadequate training in the implementation of inclusive education.

Furthermore, administrators perceived challenge number 2 as moderately difficult (median = 2.50), whereas instructors regarded it as extremely difficult (median = 4.00). In general, they perceived the implementation to be exceedingly difficult (median = 4.00) due to inadequate training in the learning process and assignments, as well as the need to contextualize learning materials to meet the requirements of students with disabilities. According to Pedrigal, et al. (2019) and Ediyanto, et al. (2021), a lack of training prevented schools from implementing curriculum modifications that were compatible with inclusive education; consequently, the learning process in the classroom did not meet the

requirements of the students in the class. Walsh (2018) nevertheless suggested that if faculty members had not yet attended training, addressing the issue of inadequate training could be accomplished through independent research and weekly brainstorming sessions with fellow members to generate new strategies.

Additionally, it is worth noting that the implementation of challenges ranging from number three to ten received a median response of three. This indicates that the lack of support from higher officials and local government units (LGUs), lack of awareness, support, and participation from parents/guardians regarding the assessment of learners' special education needs and mainstream learners with disabilities, limited interventions and services at the school level, and inadequate support from LGUs collectively constituted only moderate difficulties. Nonetheless, it was observed that administrators encountered only marginal difficulty with regard to items two through ten.

The findings suggest that there is a necessity to enhance the implementation of inclusive education for students with disabilities in order to eliminate or reduce the difficulties that arise during its operation. To achieve its objective of providing inclusive education for learner-bodied individuals (LWDs), the school requires assistance from higher authorities, including LGUs, with regard to infrastructure and facilities. This result is corroborated by Comia's (2021) study, which unveiled favorable outcomes regarding the involvement of various stakeholders in inclusive education for students with disabilities, and by Imaniah, et al. (2018), who underscored the importance of schools facilitating inclusive education having sufficient infrastructure to ensure an effective and efficient learning-oriented inclusive education for students. Furthermore, Sayson (2016) emphasized the necessity of rectifying the inadequate programs and services provided in public special education institutions for a wide range of disabilities, including those related to health. Furthermore, Toquero (2021) reached the conclusion that inclusive school policies for LWDs are essential. These challenges may be effectively tackled with the backing of higher-ranking officials.

Additionally, this suggests that parental awareness regarding inclusive education must be increased. This is supported by the findings of Gaytos, et al. (2020), which indicated that parents of children with special needs may be uninformed, unaccepted, and unwilling to participate in the program, thereby contributing to its low enrollment. Additionally, parental concerns and expectancies were identified as obstacles to the implementation of inclusive education, according to Ahamed (2021). Furthermore, Pajarillo (2019) and Comia (2021) reached the conclusion that parents played crucial roles in assisting their children in achieving their objectives.

Moreover, the lack of clarity regarding classroom-level implementation was emphasized in the research conducted by Pedrigal, et al. (2019), which concluded that school administrators must demonstrate strong leadership when attempting to implement inclusive classroom education. To ensure that learners with special needs receive quality instruction and education, a structured and methodical implementation of inclusive education must incorporate improved methods and solutions.

The study by Muega (2016) supports the notion that implementing inclusive education is complicated by the requirement for limited interventions and services, as it identified institutions where little was understood regarding the implementation of inclusion. Furthermore, Sayson (2016) disclosed that the execution of inclusive education encountered obstacles in the form of inadequate programs and services designed to meet the requirements of individuals with disabilities. According to the findings of Pedrigal et al. (2019), the school lacked sufficient resources and failed to implement curriculum adjustments that aligned with the principles of inclusive education (Ediyanto, et al., 2021).

In their presentation on the issue of inadequate monitoring of inclusive education, Gaytos et al. (2020) similarly underscored the significance of inadequate monitoring and evaluation processes. The absence of professional participation from counselors and psychologists, who played a crucial role in the referral system, exacerbated the difficulties encountered by those implementing inclusive education.

Gaytos et al. (2020) attributed the absence of efforts to improve community awareness and relations concerning special needs education to the lack of participation, acceptance, and awareness from parents of LWDs and SHS faculty members (Quinones, 2022). Conversely, a study by Pajarillo (2019) revealed that parental engagement in fostering school community relations was one of the most effective inclusive education implementation strategies employed in a school; this finding also suggests that a school administrator must demonstrate strong leadership (Pedrigal, et al., 2019). Similarly, physical facilities and apparatus were identified as one of the issues and challenges in inclusive education implementation (Allam, et al., 2021).

DISCUSSION

Based on the data gathered, the following findings were drawn:

The researcher discovered that the administrators noted that the implementation of inclusive education for learners with special educational needs was very highly implemented in terms of driving out fear, eliminating management by objectives, removing barriers to pride in workmanship, and implementing education and self-improvement. Conversely, the feedback provided by teachers and parents indicated merely a high level of implementation of all the principles. In general, the public senior high schools in Rizal demonstrated a commendable degree of execution or a high level of implementation of inclusive education for students with special educational needs, as evidenced by their adherence to all ten (10) principles of total quality management: commitment of top management, customer-focus, process management, instituting training on the job, instituting leadership, driving-out fear, elimination of management by objectives, removal

of barriers to pride in workmanship, implementation of education as a service, and making transformation a job for everyone at work.

Moreover, under commitment of top management, customer-focused, process management, implementing training on the job, implementing leadership, driving-out fear, eliminating management by objectives, and making transformation a job for everyone at work; the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. However, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis regarding the evaluation conducted by the three groups regarding the overall quality management of inclusive education in public senior high schools in the Division of Rizal, specifically for students with special educational needs, with regard to removing barriers to pride and workmanship and implementing education and self-improvement. It was apparent that administrators obtained the highest mean rank in accordance with the aforementioned principles (removing obstacles to pride in workmanship and implementing education and self-improvement), whereas teachers obtained the lowest mean rank.

Finally, the administrators and the teachers encountered very challenging situations in implementing inclusive education due to the general education instructors' inadequate preparation in managing students with disabilities, mainstreaming LWDs, and providing contextualized learning materials and learning processes. Nevertheless, they encountered only moderate difficulties in the following situations: absence of support from higher authorities and local government units; lack of parental/guardian awareness, support, and participation; limited intervention and services at the school level; unclear classroom-level implementation; absence of initiatives to improve community relations and awareness; lack of physical facilities and equipment; and inadequate monitoring and evaluation.

Conclusions

The public senior high schools in the Division of Rizal successfully implemented the Total Quality Management (TQM) approach to inclusive education for students with special educational needs during SY 2023-2024; with a certain high level of implementation in all the ten principles. Moreover, findings showed that there was no significant difference in the responses expressed by administrators, teachers, and parents regarding the implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) for inclusive education for students with special educational needs in public senior high schools in the Division of Rizal. This holds true with regard to the following principles: commitment of top management, customer-focus, process management, instituting training on the job, instituting leadership, driving-out fear, elimination of management by objectives, and making transformation a job for everyone at work. Nevertheless, administrators, teachers, and parents' evaluations of the TQM of inclusive education implementation diverged significantly with regard to the removing barriers to pride in workmanship and the implementation of education and self-improvement. And finally, due to a lack of teacher training, the administrators and the teachers in the public senior high schools in the Division of Rizal found the implementation of inclusive education for students with disabilities to be very challenging. On the other hand, lack of support from higher officials

and LGUs; lack of awareness, support, and participation from parents/guardians; limited intervention and services at the school level; unclear implementation down to the classroom level; absence of initiatives to enhance community awareness and relationships; lack of physical facilities and equipment; and a lack of support from higher officials and LGUs posed only moderate challenges for administrators and teachers during implementation.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends that educational institution may prioritize the development and empowerment of teachers with respect to the implementation of inclusive education for students with special educational requirements. Also, teachers, parents, and the entire school community may be involved in planning for inclusive education for learners with special educational needs - enhancing practices to remove barriers to pride in workmanship and implement education and self-improvement. Moreover, subsequent researchers may investigate the characteristics of participants, deficiencies, and determinants that influenced the reactions of administrators, educators, and guardians regarding the implementation of inclusive education. Lastly, future researchers may conduct research on the similar topic covering other locale. They may also conduct studies on TQM in other field of specialization.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that all research protocols involving ethics in research were complied with for the protection of all people and institutions involved in the conduct of the study. The researcher seek approval from the University's Ethics Committee prior the conduct of data gathering.

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